

Introduction to the Work with Shared Vegetation Data using the R-Package `vegetable`

M. Alvarez and K. Behn

Introduction

This document is distributed with an R-image (file `swea.rda`) including two objects for this session. For this session you have to install the package `vegetable` and its dependencies from the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN).

```
install.packages(pkgs = "vegetable", dependencies = TRUE)
```

Alternatively, you can use the package `devtools` to install the current developing version from **GitHub**.

```
library(package = "devtools")
install_github(repo = "kmapu/vegetable", dependencies = TRUE, build_vignettes = TRUE)
```

Shared Data Set

The shared data corresponds to a subset of the database **SWEA-Dataveg**, which is registered in the Global Index of Vegetation-Plot Databases (GIVD) as [AF-00-006](#) (Alvarez, Curran, and Malombe 2021). To optimize the content of the object, the data was pre-processed, whereby the most important changes regarding the original data are:

- Recorded sub-specific taxa (i.e. varieties and sub-species) have been merged with their respective species.
- Recorded supra-specific taxa (i.e. genera and families) have been skipped from the plot observations.
- Undetermined taxa are excluded.
- Multiple occurrence of a species in a plot have been merged preserving the maximum abundance value.
- Cover values have been equalized to the Braun-Blanquet scale for all records, where classes `+` and `r` have been merged with class `1`.

To start the work with the distributed data set, you need to load `vegetable` to your session.

```
library(package = vegetable)
load(file = "swea.rda")
summary(object = swea)
```

```
## ## Metadata
##   name: East African Wetlands
##   authors: K. Behn and M. Alvarez
##   year: 2021
##   object size: 419.1 Kb
##   validity: TRUE
##
## ## Content
##   number of plots: 325
##   plots with records: 325
##   variables in header: 12
```

```
## number of relations: 3
##
## ## Taxonomic List
## taxon names: 1354
## taxon concepts: 601
## validity: TRUE
```

Taxonomic Lists

Plots observations contain records of species' abundance in the respective plots. In vegetation-plot databases, those records may be collected from diverse sources and refer to different nomenclatures, thus a link between synonyms and accepted names to taxon concepts is required. Additionally, taxonomic ranks, parent-child relationships, and functional traits have to be considered for further ecological assessments. To deal with this, there is a slot called **species** including the taxonomic list in a `taxlist` object.

```
summary(object = swea@species)
```

```
## object size: 244.6 Kb
## validation of 'taxlist' object: TRUE
##
## number of taxon usage names: 1354
## number of taxon concepts: 601
## trait entries: 320
## number of trait variables: 4
## taxon views: 6
##
## concepts with parents: 599
## concepts with children: 266
##
## hierarchical levels: form < variety < subspecies < species < genus < family < phylum
## number of concepts in level form: 0
## number of concepts in level variety: 0
## number of concepts in level subspecies: 0
## number of concepts in level species: 335
## number of concepts in level genus: 202
## number of concepts in level family: 62
## number of concepts in level phylum: 2
```

In this taxonomic list you can also query for some species using its name (partial matchings are also allowed).

```
summary(object = swea@species, ConceptID = "Cyclosorus interruptus",
        secundum = "bibtexkey")
```

```
## -----
## concept ID: 50074
## view ID: 1 - CJBGSANBI2012
## level: species
## parent: 55055 Cyclosorus Link
##
## # accepted name:
## 202792 Cyclosorus interruptus (Willd.) H. Itô
##
## # synonyms (13):
## 22425 Thelypteris interrupta (Willd.) K. Iwats.
## 28798 Aspidium gongylodes Schkuhr
## 28802 Dryopteris gongylodes (Schkuhr) Kuntze
```

```
## 28807 Pteris interrupta Willd.
## 202793 Cyclosorus striatus Ching
## 205463 Aspidium continuum Desv.
## 205464 Aspidium ecklonii Kunze
## 205465 Aspidium obtusatum Sw.
## 205466 Aspidium pteroides (Retz.) Sw.
## 205467 Aspidium serra (Sw.) Sw.
## 205468 Aspidium serratum Sw.
## 205469 Aspidium unitum (L.) Sw.
## 205470 Nephrodium propinquum R. Br.
## -----
```

This summary shows the ID of the taxon (taxon concept ID), the taxon view (reference used for the nomenclature), its taxonomic rank (level), the parent taxon (the parent genus in this case), the accepted name and a list of synonyms (both including usage name ID).

You can also use the function `indented_list()` to have an overview of the hierarchical structure including this taxon.

```
indented_list(object = swea@species, filter = "Cyclosorus")
```

```
## Pteridophyta NA
## Thelypteridaceae NA
## Cyclosorus Link
## Cyclosorus interruptus (Willd.) H. Itô
```

For more details on the structure of `taxlist` objects, see [Alvarez and Luebert \(2018\)](#).

Header and Relations

Information related to plot observations (e.g. soil properties, slope, exposition, coordinates) is stored as a `data.frame` in the slot **header**. In this column-oriented table the variable **ReleveID** represents the primary key.

```
head(x = swea@header)
```

```
## ReleveID original_number record_date plot_size elevation cover_total
## 157 259 <NA> 2012-04-25 4 348 100
## 212 249 <NA> 2012-04-18 4 351 100
## 213 246 <NA> 2012-04-18 4 333 100
## 214 245 <NA> 2012-04-18 4 343 100
## 215 250 <NA> 2012-04-18 4 351 100
## 216 221 <NA> 2012-03-27 4 337 90
## community_type height_total longitude latitude country_code data_source
## 157 397 NA 38.32523 -5.084125 TZA 1
## 212 390 NA 38.32692 -5.076853 TZA 1
## 213 390 NA 38.32741 -5.075487 TZA 1
## 214 390 NA 38.32727 -5.075572 TZA 1
## 215 390 NA 38.32692 -5.076853 TZA 1
## 216 390 NA 38.32638 -5.077153 TZA 1
```

Categorical variables in **header** may need detailed descriptions on their respective classes, if they are factorized. For this purpose, a slot called **relations** contains the respective data frames. Both the data frame in the slot **relations** and the variable shared with slot **header** have the same name.

```
names(x = swea@relations)
```

```
## [1] "community_type" "country_code" "data_source"
```

For instance the field **country_code** has a relation of the same name with an homonymous primary key. This field works then as a foreign key in slot **header**.

```
head(x = swea@relations$country_code)
```

##	country_code	name_short	name_long
## 17	KEN	Kenya	Kenya
## 20	TZA	Tanzania	Tanzania
## 33	COD	Dem. Rep. Congo	Democratic Republic of the Congo
## 38	ZAF	South Africa	South Africa
## 82	ZMB	Zambia	Zambia
## 125	BDI	Burundi	Burundi

Samples

The core of plot observations is the record of taxa (usually plant species) indicating either their occurrence or their abundance in the respective plots. Since *vegetable* objects emulate relational databases, this information is contained in column-oriented table, at the slot **samples**.

```
head(x = swea@samples)
```

##	ReleveID	TaxonUsageID	cover_percentage	cover_class
## 15	3661	461	5	1
## 16	3662	461	2	1
## 17	3663	461	1	1
## 18	3748	461	1	1
## 19	3750	461	1	1
## 21	3817	461	5	1

In this table, the variable **ReleveID** is pointing to the plot observations in slot **header**, while the variable **TaxonUsageID** is linked to the slot **species**. The later is rather a mention of the taxon usage name recorded in the plot, which will be recognized either as synonym or accepted name of a taxon concept. The abundance of the species in plots (variable **cover_class**) corresponds to the Braun-Blanquet scale with the classes “+” and “r” merged with “1,” as previously mentioned.

Cocktail Classification

Cocktail classification is a supervised classification method based on logical algorithms. The main elements in these algorithms are the definition of species groups (cocktail groups) and dominant species. The algorithms will recognize plot observations in a vegetation unit by the occurrence of more than a half of the members of a cocktail group, the absence of a group and whether a dominant species is present over a cut-level of abundance or not (Bruehlheide 1997; Kočí, Chytrý, and Tichý 2003).

The package *vegetable* defines an object class called *shaker*. This object will always depend on a *vegetable* object (companion). A *shaker* is included in the distributed image, which is called *syntax*.

```
summary(object = syntax, companion = swea)
```

The design of cocktail algorithms is a time-consuming, iterative process and will not be explained here. We recommend to use the software **Juice** for this purpose (Tichý 2002). The function `make_cocktail()` will execute the expert system and produce the classification that can be inserted in the data set.

```
swea@header <- make_cocktail(shaker = syntax, vegetable = swea, cover = "cover_class",
                           syntax = "veg_unit")
```

For every formula contained in *syntax*, a binary variable indicating whether a plot is belonging to a vegetation unit or not. Additionally a column defined as **veg_unit** is inserted with the name of the respective units. Note

that in this column observations that are not recognized in any vegetation unit get a **NA** value, while observation recognized in more than one unit get a **+** symbol.

```
summary(object = as.factor(x = swea$veg_unit))
```

```
##          + 01Isc-Fim 02Fui-Amm 03Cor-Pan 04Gra-Ipo 05Cen-Per 06Cyp-Cyp 07Cyp-Fui
##          36         11          8         17          8         12         59         42
## 08Mel-Lee 09Cyp-lat 10Cyp-Dry 11Phr-mau 12PhrEch 13Vig-Pan
##          19         25         50         22          5         11
```

Statistics from Taxon Traits

Life Forms and Origin

The taxonomic list includes information on life forms and origin (native or introduced to sub-Saharan Africa). This information can be summarized for every plot, for instance calculating the proportion of life forms, weighted by the abundance. For it, we can use the function `trait_proportion()`, which will aggregate proportions of single life form classes into plot observations. Since we like to collect the information in the slot `header` with further plot properties, we will use the option `in_header=TRUE`.

```
swea <- trait_proportion(trait = "life_form", object = swea, weight = "cover_class",
                        in_header = TRUE)

# Boxplot
par(las = 1, mar = c(4, 8, 1, 1))
boxplot(formula = obligate_annual_prop ~ veg_unit, data = swea$header, horizontal = TRUE,
        col = "grey", ylab = "", xlab = "Proportion of Annual Plants")
abline(v = 0.5, lty = "dashed")
```


Note that `trait_proportion()` is designed to calculate proportions of categorical traits. Alternatively the function `trait_stats()` is suitable for statistics of numerical traits (e.g. calculation of weighted averages).

Taxonomy

Taxonomic information is not mandatory in taxonomic lists. In slot **species** of the object `swea` both, the taxonomic ranks and the parent-child relationships are included.

```
summary(object = swea@species)
```

```
## object size: 244.6 Kb
## validation of 'taxlist' object: TRUE
##
## number of taxon usage names: 1354
## number of taxon concepts: 601
## trait entries: 320
## number of trait variables: 4
## taxon views: 6
##
## concepts with parents: 599
## concepts with children: 266
##
## hierarchical levels: form < variety < subspecies < species < genus < family < phylum
## number of concepts in level form: 0
## number of concepts in level variety: 0
## number of concepts in level subspecies: 0
## number of concepts in level species: 335
## number of concepts in level genus: 202
## number of concepts in level family: 62
## number of concepts in level phylum: 2
```

For statistical assessments it is necessary to set taxonomic information as species traits. This can be managed with the function `tax2traits()`.

```
swea@species <- tax2traits(object = swea@species, get_names = TRUE)
head(x = swea@species@taxonTraits)
```

```
##   TaxonConceptID   life_form origin_ssa origin_source
## 2             56944 tussock_plant   native           3
## 4             56931 tussock_plant   native           3
## 6             56768 tussock_plant   native           3
## 8              249 tussock_plant   native           3
## 9             54697 tussock_plant   native           3
## 10            52150 annual_plant  adventive         3
##               origin_remarks                species    genus    family
## 2                <NA>   Anosporum pectinatum Anosporum Cyperaceae
## 4                <NA>         Carex mannii     Carex Cyperaceae
## 6                <NA>   Cyperus platycaulis   Cyperus Cyperaceae
## 8                <NA>   Epilobium salignum Epilobium Onagraceae
## 9                <NA> Epilobium stereophyllum Epilobium Onagraceae
## 10 Mexico to S. Tropical America Erigeron sumatrensis Erigeron Compositae
##               phylum
## 2 Magnoliophyta
## 4 Magnoliophyta
## 6 Magnoliophyta
## 8 Magnoliophyta
```

```
## 9 Magnoliophyta
## 10 Magnoliophyta
```

The last function inserted new columns for taxonomic ranks indicating the usage name of each taxon (without author name) and its respective parent taxa. In the next step we will calculate the frequency of species in each family.

```
# Counting species per family
Families <- count_taxa(object = species ~ family, data = swea@species)

# Sorting families by frequency
Families <- Families[order(Families$species_count, decreasing = TRUE), ]

# Plotting the 20 most frequent families
par(las = 2, mar = c(10, 5, 1, 1))
with(data = Families[1:20,], expr = barplot(species_count, names.arg = family,
      ylab = "Number of Species"))
```


To see if there is some trend in the proportion of a family, for instance Poaceae, we can use again the function `trait_proportion()`. Herewith we will weight the proportion of families by the abundance of the respective species in the plot.

```
swea <- trait_proportion(trait = "family", object = swea, weight = "cover_class",
  in_header = TRUE)

# Boxplot
par(las = 1, mar = c(4, 8, 1, 1))
boxplot(formula = Poaceae_prop ~ veg_unit, data = swea@header, horizontal = TRUE,
  col = "grey", ylab = "", xlab = "Proportion of Grasses")
abline(v = 0.5, lty = "dashed")
```


Export Functions

The structure of `vegetable` objects is quite complex and some assessments or displays will require a proper export method. Here we introduce some of the basic ways to export information for further assessments. For instance, some of those functions will work on a subset of plots, which include the species *Cyperus papyrus* L.

```
cype_pap <- subset(x = swea, subset = TaxonName == "Cyperus papyrus", slot = "taxonNames")
```

In the previous step only records for *C. papyrus* are preserved, thus we will use the plot observation ids to produce a subset with full relevés.

```
cype_pap <- subset(x = swea, subset = ReveleID %in% cype_pap$ReleveID, slot = "header")
```

Cross-table

The most common format for displaying vegetation data is the cross table, with species as rows and plots as columns. To produce cross tables there is the function `crosstable()`. This function requires a formula in the form *abundance twiddles species and plot* (in the example, `cover_class ~ ReveleID + AcceptedName`) and a function to summarize multiple occurrences of a species in a plot (e.g. the maximum value). Depending on the size of the data set, this process may require some seconds.

```
Table <- crosstable(formula = cover_class ~ ReveleID + AcceptedName, data = cype_pap, FUN = max)
```

Note that the terms **ReleveID** and **AcceptedName** are the key variables for the slot **header** and the object **taxlist** in slot **species**, respectively.

It is also possible to insert additional columns besides the species list, for instance to add the author name (**AuthorName** in **taxlist**) and the family, you need to add them as terms in the formula.

```
Table <- crosstable(formula = cover_class ~ ReveleID + AcceptedName + AuthorName + family,
  data = cype_pap, FUN = max, na_to_zero = TRUE)
```

```
# First 5 rows and 10 columns
```

```
Table[1:5, 1:10]
```

##	AcceptedName	AuthorName	family	3796	3847	3856	3866
## 1	Thunbergia alata	Bojer ex Sims	Acanthaceae	2	1	1	1
## 2	Acanthus polystachyus	Delile	Acanthaceae	0	0	0	0
## 3	Alternanthera sessilis (L.) R. Br. ex DC.	Amaranthaceae		0	0	0	0
## 4	Oenanthe palustris (Chiov.) C. Norman	Apiaceae		0	0	0	0
## 5	Gomphocarpus semilunatus	A. Rich.	Apocynaceae	0	0	0	0
##	3879	3881	3850				
## 1	1	0	0				
## 2	0	1	0				
## 3	0	0	1				
## 4	0	0	1				
## 5	0	0	0				

Some statistical software and R-packages may need the first cross table but transposed. This can be achieved by changing the formula in the function.

```
Table <- crosstable(formula = cover_class ~ AcceptedName + ReveleID, data = swea,
  FUN = max, as_matrix = TRUE)
```

Juice table

There is also a possibility to export the content of plot observations to **Juice**. Juice is a freeware specialized in the analysis of vegetation-plot data sets and implement a series of statistical assessment methods. To produce the data sets, there is the function `write_juice()`, which is working in a similar way as `crosstable()`. Here we need additionally to specify which header variables will be exported and which are the geographical coordinates (assumed as decimal degrees in WGS84).

```
write_juice(data = swea, file = "swea", formula = cover_class ~ ReveleID + AcceptedName,
  db_name = swea@description$name,
  header = c("country_code", "data_source", "record_date", "plot_size", "elevation",
    "veg_unit"),
  coords = c("longitude", "latitude"), FUN = max)
```

This command will produce two files in your working directory, the file **swea_table.txt** with the cross table, and **swea_header.txt** with the information of plots (also called header table). To import those files to Juice, you need to follow these steps.

Map

The plot observations included in this data set are geo-referenced, where the exactitude of the location is depending on the data source (some data are geo-referenced according to the study site description of the respective publication).

The location of plot observations can be mapped by using the package `leaflet`.

```
library(package = leaflet)
leaflet(data = swea@header) %>%
  addTiles() %>%
  addCircleMarkers(lng = ~longitude, lat = ~latitude, color = "red",
    opacity = 0.3, radius = 1.5)
```


References

- Alvarez, Miguel, Michael Curran, and Itambo Malombe. 2021. "SWEA-Dataveg: A Vegetation Database for sub-Saharan Africa." *Vegetation Classification and Survey* 2: 59–63. <https://doi.org/10.3897/vcs/2021/64911>.
- Alvarez, Miguel, and Federico Luebert. 2018. "The Taxlist Package: Managing Plant Taxonomic Lists in R." *Biodiversity Data Journal* 6: e23635. <https://doi.org/10.3897/bdj.6.e23635>.
- Bruelheide, Helge. 1997. "Using Formal Logic to Classify Vegetation." *Folia Geobotanica Et Phytotaxonomica* 32: 41–46.
- Kočí, Martin, Milan Chytrý, and Lubomír Tichý. 2003. "Formalized Reproduction of an Expert-Based Phytosociological Classification: A Case Study of Subalpine Tall-Forb Vegetation." *Journal of Vegetation Science* 14 (4): 601–10. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2003.tb02187.x>.
- Tichý, Lubomír. 2002. "JUICE, Software for Vegetation Classification." *Journal of Vegetation Science* 13 (3): 451–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2002.tb02069.x>.